

EDUCATIONAL POTENTIAL OF ETHNO DESIGN IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE DESIGNERS

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Abstract. The article explores the importance of improving the system of professional training of future designers and the education of students, taking into account national culture and design in the process of educational activities. The authors draw attention to the fact that the integration of national values and traditions into the learning process can significantly enrich students' experience and contribute to a more successful mastery of knowledge in the field of design. The researchers analyze how this approach can contribute to improving the quality of education and developing professional skills in future professionals.

Keywords: national-patriotic education, ethno design, professional skills, design, national culture, upbringing.

In the modern world, design plays an important role in shaping the visual environment that meets the needs of society. In this regard, the task of training highly qualified designers capable of creating unique projects that combine tradition and modernity is becoming increasingly important. One of the most effective approaches is to integrate ethno-design into the educational process, which helps to develop professional skills and at the same time foster respect for national culture in students.

Ethno design combines national traditions with modern design trends, providing a link between cultural heritage and innovation. I. Syvash defines ethno design as “an appeal to folk art, ethnic motifs as a source of inspiration; the use of stylistic, decorative, formative techniques of folk crafts in works of graphic, industrial design, interior design, fashion design, etc.” (Syvash, 2019, p. 118).

According to A. Rudchenko, ethno design is a form of creative activity based on folk traditions, synthesizing artistic and technical components and involving mass replication of products with a pronounced ethnic component (Rudenchenko, 2014).

Ethno design performs a number of important functions in the professional training of future designers:

Cultural and educational. Acquaintance with traditional techniques, ornaments, colors and crafts enriches students' worldview and shapes their understanding of national identity.

Creative and innovative. The use of ethno-design elements in project activities promotes the development of creative thinking and the ability to adapt cultural traditions to modern needs.

Educational. Integrating ethnic motifs into educational tasks fosters respect for cultural heritage, develops patriotism and social responsibility.

Professional training of designers requires a harmonious combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Ethno design allows students to:

- get acquainted with the cultural heritage of their country by exploring traditional ornaments, materials, shapes and colors;
- learn how to integrate elements of ethnic style into modern design, creating products that meet the needs of the modern market;
- develop creativity and innovative thinking, combining the past with the present.

Ethno design has a significant educational potential. It helps students to develop respect for national culture, patriotism, and pride in their origins. The use of ethnic motifs in design projects helps students realize the connection between cultural traditions and modern design practices. In addition, ethno design stimulates the development of social responsibility in future professionals, as the popularization of national traditions through design contributes to their preservation and development.

Ethnodesign can be effectively integrated into curricula through the following approaches:

- Studying the theory. Inclusion in lecture courses (for example, within the disciplines “History of Art” and “History of Design”) covering the history of national art, techniques for making traditional products, and features of decorative and applied art.
- Practical classes. Implementation of student projects using elements of ethno-design, which allows students to consolidate their knowledge in practice.
- Master classes. Collaboration with folk artists to pass on practical skills and knowledge of craft techniques to students.
- Competitions and exhibitions. Involving students in presenting their works in the format of exhibitions, as well as visiting exhibitions of folk art masters, which helps to popularize national culture.

Integration of national values and traditions into the educational process can greatly enrich students' experience and contribute to a more successful mastery of design knowledge:

1) It promotes the development of a deep understanding of culture:

- Immersion in historical and cultural heritage: The study of national traditions and art allows students to understand the origins of modern design, its aesthetic and functional foundations.
- Formation of cultural identity: Integration of national values into the curriculum helps students to realize their belonging to a particular culture and its significance in the global context.

2) It increases creativity and innovation:

- An innovative approach to traditions: Familiarization with national crafts, ornaments, textures, and techniques stimulates students to create original and modern design solutions.
- Cultural resource for creativity: National traditions become a source of inspiration for generating unique ideas and projects.

3) Practical implementation of knowledge:

- Application of ethnic elements in modern design: Students learn how to adapt national motifs to real-life orders in the field of graphic design.
- Creating competitive products: Taking into account ethnic characteristics allows you to create unique products that attract attention in local and international markets.

4) Increasing motivation to learn:

- Involvement in real projects: students who see the practical application of ethnodesign elements become more interested in learning.
- Emotional involvement: learning about one's own culture makes one proud and interested in mastering the profession more deeply.

5) Development of intercultural competence:

- Studying different ethnic styles: in the process of studying, students get acquainted not only with their own culture, but also with the traditions of other nations, which develops their worldview and prepares them to work in a globalized world.
- Interaction of cultures: Integration of national values builds the ability to creatively adapt traditional motifs in intercultural projects.

6) Formation of professional competencies:

- Harmony between aesthetics and functionality: studying traditional forms, materials, and techniques allows students to create projects that meet aesthetic and practical requirements.
- Ability to use local resources: Integration of national traditions helps students

master techniques specific to their region, making them more competitive in the local market.

7) Aesthetic education:

- Understanding harmony: ethnodesign teaches students to find a balance between traditional motifs and modern trends, developing their sense of style and aesthetic taste.
- Enrichment of visual language: involvement in work with national motifs allows students to master a variety of visual techniques and images.

8) Social responsibility and heritage preservation:

- Promotion of cultural heritage: Integration of ethno design into the educational process helps future designers to realize their role in preserving and promoting national traditions.

Thus, the integration of national values and traditions into the learning process is an important source of enriching the professional experience of design students. Ethno design is a powerful tool in the professional training of future designers, contributing to the formation of not only professional competencies, but also moral values and cultural identity. Integration of national traditions into the educational process allows preserving cultural heritage, promoting its development and popularization. This approach improves the quality of education, develops the creative potential of students and creates highly qualified professionals capable of working effectively in the modern world.

References

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